

“EFFECT OF DIFFERENT PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS ON FLOWERING, FRUIT SET AND PHYSICAL QUALITY OF SWEET ORANGE (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbek)”Pratiksha Dakhore¹, Dr. S. J. Shinde², Dr. S. R. Barkule³¹M.Sc.(Horticulture) Scholor, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtrapratikshadakhore01997@gmail.com²Assistant Professor, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtrasrbarkule@gmail.com³Associate Professor, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtrashivshinde72@gmail.com

(MS Received: 26.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:01.01.2024)

MS 3151

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE)

Abstract

The experiment was conducted to study the effect of different plant growth regulators on flowering and fruit set of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) at Central Nursery Scheme, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani during the year 2022-2023. The experiment consists of 9 treatments with 3 replications in randomized block design (RBD). The foliar application of different plant growth regulators at unopen bud stage, full bloom stage and fruit set stage. The experimental findings revealed that, among the different plant growth regulators NAA @ 100 ppm (T₂) recorded the minimum days required for fruit set (8.67 days) and the maximum number of flowers (8509.00). The CPPU @ 3 ppm (T₃) recorded maximum fruit set (29.01 %), fruit retention (20.96 %), fruit weight (215.76 g), fruit length (8.20 cm), fruit diameter (8.06 cm), number of segment (14.21), fruit juice (49.69 %), minimum fruit drop (61.02 %), pomace weight (35.66 g), rind weight (68.17 g). The minimum number of seed (18.73) was found in GA₃ @ 100 ppm (T₁).

Keywords: Growth regulators, *Citrus sinensis*, Flower, fruit, CPPU, NAA.

Introduction

The sweet orange, or *Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck, is a member of the Rutaceae family. It is grown in tropical and subtropical climates all over the world. The principle growing states for sweet oranges are Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Punjab, Haryana, and Rajasthan. The principal edible portion of a citrus fruit is the juice present in the juice vesicles. Commercial pectin and essential oils are made from the rind of the citrus fruits. The noteworthy medicinal research reveals that eating citrus can reduce risk of heart attack and strokes. The inner white peel and the rag of oranges when consumed along with the juice, it helps to relieve constipation, serving as laxative. The chemical composition of sweet orange shows that it contains water (89.2 %), sugar (58 %), pectin (1-2 %), glycosides (0.1-1.5 %), pentosans (0.8-1.2 %), citric acid (0.4 to 1.5 %), fibre (0.6-0.9 %), proteins (0.6-0.8 %), fat (0.2-0.5 %), minerals (0.5-0.9 %) and essential oils (0.2-0.5 %) and TSS (10-12° Brix) (Syed *et al.*, 2012). Nutrient deficiency disturbs the production of plant growth regulators which controls the size, colour and premature fruit drop. Excessive premature fruit drop is also dependent on 3 other factors like high temperature and water deficits, insect/pest attack, and wind velocity of the area (Ashraf *et al.*, 2015). Use of plant growth regulators along with micronutrients have a significant effect to improve quality of citrus fruits (Singh and Misra, 1986). As the fruit size in early stage is very small, the dropping is minimal. However, it is very severe when fruits are of medium size and whole area under citrus is covered with dropped fruits. The application of plant growth regulators is effective in reducing the excessive premature fruit drop. Plant growth regulators like 2,4 dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) and salicylic acid (SA) have been reported to be effective in controlling fruit drop in citrus (Ashraf *et al.*, 2015). Other plant growth regulators which are being used to prevent fruit drop include 2,4,5 trichlorophenoxypropionic acid (2, 4, 5-TPA), naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), and gibberellic acid (GA) (Michael *et al.*, 1999). Similarly, deficiency of micronutrients (Zn, Cu, Fe, and Mn) in the soil of citrus orchards also affects the fruit yield, quality and fruit drop. Foliar application of Zn can improve the citrus fruit yield and quality and control the premature fruit drop. The triacontanol has potential function in regulating and modifying various physiological processes in plant and enhancing flowering yield (Angrej Ali *et al.* 2021). The application of KNO₃ found to be best management strategy for getting higher quality production and productivity and it can be beneficial for effective

and economic management practices for sweet orange (Sable *et al.* (2022). The N-(2-Chloro-4-pyridyl)-N-phenylurea (CPPU) is a very active cytokinin-like plant growth regulator that encourages chlorophyll production, cell division, and cell expansion. It also promotes the fruit set and quickens fruit growth (Zeng *et al.* 2016). Hence the present investigation employing selection of appropriate plant growth regulators, their quantity and method of application was undertaken with an objective to find out effect on flowering, fruit set and physical quality of fruit.

Material And Methods

The field experiment on sweet orange was carried out at Central Nursery Scheme, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani during the year of 2022-2023. The experiment consists of 9 treatments viz. (T₁) GA₃ 10 ppm, (T₂) NAA @ 100 ppm, (T₃) CPPU @ 3 ppm, (T₄) Salicylic acid @ 100 ppm, (T₅) Triacontanol @ 500 ppm, (T₆) Boron @ 0.2%, (T₇) ZnSO₄ @ 0.5%, (T₈) KNO₃ @ 0.1%, (T₉) Control with 03 replications in randomized block design (RBD). There was one plant per treatment per replication.

The foliar application of different plant growth regulators at unopen bud stage, full bloom stage and fruit set stage there were three spray schedules. Each tree was sprayed heavily by taking care to wet the complete tree. Ten years old uniformly grown trees spaced at 6 m x 6 m were selected for present study. They were kept under uniform conditions of orchard management during the study period where all the agronomic practices were carried out as per package of practices.

The observations of flower and fruit parameters (Days required for flower initiation, Days required for initiation of 50 per cent flowering, Days required for fruit set from flowering, Number of flowers, Fruit set %, Fruit retention %, Fruit drop %, Weight of fruit g, Length of fruit cm, Diameter of fruit cm, Number of segments per fruit, Fruit juice %, Number of seed per fruits, Weight of pomace g, Weight of rind g) are taken as per protocol. Data obtained on various variables of flower, fruit set and physical quality of fruits were recorded, analyzed by analysis of variance of randomized block design as suggested by Panse and Sukhatme, 1995

Result And Discussion

The perusal of the data presented in Table 1 and 2 regarding flowering, fruit set and physical quality of fruits as influence by different plant regulators are discussed below

Days required for flower initiation

The data presented in the Table 1 showed that the minimum days required for flower initiation (65.57 days) observed in the treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) which was non-significant. Whereas, maximum days required for flower initiation (72.67 days) observed in the treatment T₉ (Control).

Days required for 50 % flowering

The significant effect of different plant growth regulators on the days required for 50 % flowering was observed. The significantly minimum days required for 50 % flowering (16.00 days) was observed in the treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) whereas, the maximum days required for 50 % flowering (20.67 days) was observed in treatment T₉ (control). It might be due to the increased synthesis of cytokinin and auxin in the root tissue by their enhanced activity with the application of GA₃ @ 100 ppm and their simultaneous transport to the auxiliary buds would have resulted in a better sink for the mobilization of photo assimilates at a faster rate. This would have helped in the early transformation from the vegetative phase to reproductive phase. The induction of early flower bud initiation might be influenced by triggering of such metabolic processes and narrowing of the carbon: nitrogen ratio by the significant accumulation of carbohydrates (Kannan *et al.*, 2009).

The other possible reason may be that Gibberellic acid when used in citrus fruit crops stimulates both cell division, cell elongation and regulates flowering. The results are in accordance with the findings of Thirugnanavel *et al.* (2007) in acid lime,

Days required for fruit set from flowering

The data revealed that the significantly minimum days required for fruit set from flowering (8.67 days) was observed in treatment T₂ (NAA @ 100 ppm) while, maximum days required for fruit set from flowering (12.60 days) was observed in treatment T₉ (control). It might be due to NAA application because of the fact that it maintains the on-going physiological and bio-chemical process of inhibition of abscission. NAA also improves the internal physiology of developing fruits in terms of better supply of water, nutrients and other bio-compounds vital for their proper growth and development. The similar results were obtained with Patel *et al.* (2021) in kagzi lime.

Number of flowers

The significantly maximum number of flowers (8509.67 flowers) were observed in treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) whereas, minimum number of flowers (7110.33) were observed in treatment T₉ (control). Increase in number of flowers with GA₃ application might be due to fact that the plants sprayed with GA₃ remained physiologically more active to build up sufficient food reserve for developing flowers. Hence, the increase in flowering may be due to enhanced photosynthesis which increased the potential of trees to develop more flower buds. The other reason may be due to the effect of lower concentration of GA₃ on the expression of floral stimulus at the shoot apex rather than leaves. GA₃ increases the mitotic activity in sub apical meristems and thus become more responsive to photo inductive conditions. Thirugnanavel *et al.* (2007) in acid lime reported that application of GA₃ showed better performance in increasing in number of flowers per shoot. These results are in accordance with findings of Kadam *et al.* (2005) in sapota, Debbarma and Hazarika (2016) in acid lime.

Fruit set (%)

The data presented in the table showed that the significantly maximum fruit set percent (29.01 %) was observed in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) followed by treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) (28.12 %). Whereas minimum fruit set (20.24 %) was observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). It might be due to that CPPU (a synthetic cytokinin of the phenyl urea group) increases fruit set and significantly decreases fruit drop. Significant effect on highest fruit set was also reported by

Nimbolkar *et al.* (2015) in pear fruit cv. Gola

Fruit retention (%)

The maximum fruit retention (20.96 %) was obtained in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) followed by the treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) (19.46 %). Whereas minimum fruit retention (12.32 %) was observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). Significant effect on fruit retention % was found in foliar application of CPPU @ 3 ppm. It might be due to that CPPU (a synthetic cytokinin of the phenyl urea group) increases fruit retention. An exogenous application of CPPU acts early cell division in the fruit and also on subsequent growth thus, fruit becomes able to attract so much water, minerals and carbohydrates that enable the fruit for better retention up to maturity stage (Greene, 2001).

Fruit drop %

The results showed that the significantly minimum fruit drop percentage (61.02 %) was observed in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) which was found at par with the treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) (62.56 %) and treatment T₈ (KNO₃ @ 0.1%) (63.18 %). Whereas, highest fruit drop percentage was observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). Significant effect on lowering the fruit drop was also reported by Nimbolkar *et al.* (2015) in pear fruit cv. Gola as the experiment reported the lowering the amount of fruit drop significantly. It might be due to that CPPU (a synthetic cytokinin of the phenyl urea group) increases fruit set and significantly decreases fruit drop.

Fruit weight (g)

The effect of different plant growth regulators on fruit weight of sweet orange found significant value. Significantly maximum fruit weight (215.76 g) observed in the treatment T₃. While, the minimum fruit weight (179.11 g) was observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). Foliar application of CPPU @ 3 ppm significantly increases in weight of fruits. This result might be due to that CPPU (a synthetic cytokinin of the phenyl urea group) increases fruit weight and significantly with ample supply of metabolites which helps in growth and development, increases cell size and is also responsible for the production and transport of plant sugars that increased the weight of fruit. The results were found similar with Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota, Smith (2008) and Rafaat *et al.* (2012) in grapes

Fruit length (cm)

The significantly maximum fruit length (8.20 cm) was observed in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) but, minimum fruit length (6.89 cm) was observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). The application of CPPU might be advantageous due to its beneficial effects on promoting cell elongation and division as well as its important role in triggering protein, RNA and DNA biosynthesis. The results are true with the results of Nimbolkar *et al.* (2015) in pear fruit and Rafaat *et al.* (2012) in grapes.

Fruit diameter (cm)

The higher fruit girth (8.06 cm) observed in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) which was found at par with the treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) (7.90 cm). Whereas, lower fruit girth (6.81 cm) was found in the treatment T₉ (Control). Similar results have been reported by Wu *et al.*, (2020) in kiwifruit. This result might be seen due to CPPU is responsible for the production and transport of plant sugars which cause an increase in cell size and stimulate cell division and cell elongation.

Number of segments per fruit

The data presented in the table no 2 showed that the significant effect on the number of segments per fruit. Significantly maximum number of segments per fruit (14.21) was observed in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) but, minimum number of segments per fruit (10.02) observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). It was evident from the recorded data that, there was significantly increase in number of segments per fruit due to the spraying of CPPU @ 6 ppm. This might be because CPPU treatments affects fruit set, fruit retention, fruit growth and fruit

development, which causes a greater quantity of large-sized fruits to mature and be ready for harvest, similar results were as found by Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota and Nimbolkar *et al.* (2015).

Fruit juice (%)

The maximum fruit juice percentage (49.69 %) was observed in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) whereas, minimum fruit juice percentage (38.71 %) was observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). This result might be seen due to CPPU is responsible for the production and transport of plant sugars which cause an increase in cell size and stimulate cell division and cell elongation. Similar results have been reported by Wu *et al.*, (2020) found similar result in kiwifruit and grapevine respectively.

Number of seed per fruit

Among the treatments, the treatment T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) showed that the significantly minimum number of seed per fruit (18.73 seeds) which was at par with treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) (18.92 seeds) and T₈ (KNO₃ @ 0.1%) (19.36 seeds). Whereas the treatment T₉ (Control) treatment shows the maximum number of seed per fruit (25.82 seeds) among all treatment. The reduction in the number of seeds per fruit may be due to the stimulatory effect of GA₃ on parthenocarpic fruit development (Zhang, 2003). The other possible reason for a smaller number of seeds per fruit with GA₃ and micronutrients might be due to their involvement in hormonal metabolism, increased cell division, elongation and expansion of cells. The results are in accordance with the findings reported Shinde *et al.* (2008) in Kagzi Lime,

Weight of pomace (g)

The data presented in the table no. 2 showed that the significantly minimum weight of pomace (35.66 g) found in treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm), while the treatment T₉ (control) treatment noted the maximum weight of pomace (38.81 g) among all treatments. The possible explanation for increase in pulp-stone ratio might be due to faster movement of simple sugars into fruit and cell expansion by CPPU as it increases cell size and is also responsible for the production and transport of plant sugars that increased the weight of fruit. The results are in accordance with the findings reported by Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota.

Weight of rind (g)

Minimum weight of rind (68.17 g) was found in treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm), but the treatment T₉ (control) treatment shows the maximum weight of the rind (72.23) among all treatment. The possible explanation for increase in pulp-stone ratio might be due to faster movement of simple sugars into fruit and cell expansion by CPPU as it increases cell size and is also responsible for the production and transport of plant sugars that increased the weight of fruit. The results are in accordance with the findings reported by Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota.

References

- Ashraf M. Y., Ilyas A., Hussain M., Ashraf M., Ahmed R., and Kamal A. (2015). Effect of micronutrients (Zn, Cu and B) on photosynthetic and fruit yield attributes of citrus reticulata Blanco var. kinnow. Pak. J. Bot., 47(4), 1241-1247.
- Angrej A., Kumar A., Rasool K., Ganai N. A., Lone I. H., Baba T. R., Hamid M., Asrar-ul H. and Lone J. A. (2021). Triacantanol spray mediated plant growth and productivity in fruits crops: *TPI*, 10(7):789-792.
- Arjun Reddy N. R., Vijaychandra Reddy S. 2, V. Sitarambabu 1, K. N. Sreenivasulu 3 2023 "A Study On Socio-Economic Status Of Sweet Orange Farmers In Anantapuramu District" Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxvii, July 2023 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, PP 942-944.
- Barkule S. R., Patel B. N. and Baghele R. D. (2018). Effect of 28-Homobrassinolide, CPPU, GA₃ and Humic Acid on Quality and Shelf-Life of Sapota (*Manilkara achras*) cv. Kalipatti. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences. Special Issue-6:962-967*.
- D.D. Diwate¹, M.B. Patil², S.G. Patil³ D.P. Deshpande⁴, 2018, Response Of Soil And Foliar Application Of Silicon On Growth And Yield Parameters Of Sweet Orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) CV. Nucellar, Vol. Viii, Issue Xxvii, Oct 2018 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, PP 164-169.
- Kadam D. D., Garad B. V., Jadhav Y. R., Mangave K. K. and Patgaonkar D. R. (2005). Influence of growth regulators on flowering behaviour of sapota under semi- arid zone of Maharashtra. *J. Soil and Crops*. 15(1): 111-114.
- Kannan K., Jawaharlal M. and Prabhu M. (2009). Effect of plant growth regulators on growth and yield parameters of paprika cv. ktpl-19. *Agric. Sci. Digest*, 29 (3): 157-162.
- Michael (1999). The influence of exogenously applied 2,4-D and NAA on fruit drop reduction in pummelo. *ISSN: 1553*
- Nimbolkar P. K., Rai P. N., Mishra D. S. and Singh S. K. (2015). Influence of plant bioregulators on yield, physico-chemical attributes and post-harvest quality of pear cv. Gola under Terai region of Northern India. *Indian J. Hort.*, 72(4) 485488.
- Panse V. G. and Sukhatme P. V. (1995). Randomized designs and square and statistical methods for agricultural workers (2nd Edition). Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi. Pp 34- 153
- Rafaat, Ghada S. S. and Ola A. A. (2012). Effect of foliar spraying with gibberellic acid and or sitofex on bud behaviour, vegetative growth, yield and cluster quality of Thompson Seedless grapevines. *Journal of American Science*, 8 (5):21-34.
- Sable S. V., Temak S. D., Girase L. A and Naglot U. M. (2022). Effect of different chemicals on growth and yield parameters of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck) Var. Nucellar. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 11(3): 1280-1283.
- S.S. Shilewanti, and V.D. Patil, 2020, Effect Of Soil And Foliar Feeding Of Nutrients Through Organic And Inorganic Sources On Yield And Quality Of Sweet Orange (*Citrus Sinensis* L. Osbeck) Vol. IX, Issue Xxxii, Jan 2020 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, PP 343-345.
- Shinde B. B., Ingle H. V., Dhawale D. U., Hajare A. R., and Dhobe S. G. (2008). Effect of plant growth regulators on size, yield and quality of acid lime. *Journal of soils and Crops*, 18 (1), 117-120.
- Smith Rhonda (2008). The use of CPPU in wine grapes to increased fruit set. UC cooperative extension Sonoma country, 133 aviation blvd, suite 109, santa rosa, ca 94503: 1-4.
- Somwanshi B. S., Patil M. B., Nainwad R. V. and Shinde S. E. (2017). Effect of different chemicals on pre-harvest fruit drop and fruit set of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck.) var. Nucellar. *IJCS*, 5(4): 168-171..
- Wu. L., Lan J., Xiang X., Xiang H., Jin Z. and Khan S. (2020) Transcriptome sequencing and endogenous phytohormone analysis reveal new insights in CPPU controlling fruit development in kiwifruit (*Actinidia chinensis*). *PLOS ONE* 15(10): e0240355.
- Zeng H., Yang W., Lu C., Lin W., Zou M., Zhang H., Wan J. and Huang X. (2016). Effect of CPPU on Carbohydrate and Endogenous Hormone Levels in Young Macadamia Fruit. *PLOS ONE* 11(7): e0158705. doi: 10.1371/ journal. pone.0158705.
- Zhang Y., Chen K. S., Zhang S. L., and Ferguson I. (2003). The role of salicylic acid in postharvest ripening of Kiwi fruit. *Postharvest Biol. Technol.*, 28:67-74.

Table 1: Effect of different plant growth regulators on flowering and fruit set in sweet orange .

Tr. No.	Treatments	Days required for flower initiation	Days required for 50 % flowering	Days required for fruit set from flowering	Number of flowers	Fruit set(%)	Fruit retention	Fruit Drop (%)
T ₁	GA ₃ (100 ppm)	65.57	16.00	9.67	8509.67	28.12	19.46	62.56
T ₂	NAA (100 ppm)	68.08	17.33	8.67	7773.00	24.78	15.39	64.32
T ₃	CPPU (3 ppm)	66.11	16.70	9.00	8099.00	29.01	20.96	61.02
T ₄	Salicylic acid (100 ppm)	69.67	19.66	11.67	7247.67	22.62	13.64	66.90
T ₅	Triacantanol (500 ppm)	71.17	19.67	10.67	7558.67	23.16	14.76	65.58
T ₆	Boron (0.2%)	72.17	20.00	11.00	7379.33	23.00	14.56	66.12
T ₇	ZnSO ₄ (0.5%)	69.42	19.33	10.33	7989.67	24.01	15.02	64.96
T ₈	KNO ₃ (0.1%)	68.50	18.33	9.33	7943.33	26.24	19.00	63.18
T ₉	Control	72.67	20.67	12.60	7110.33	20.24	12.32	67.20
S.E m. ±		3.95	0.24	0.15	245.94	0.29	0.13	0.91
C.D. at 5 %		NS	0.73	0.46	740.34	0.87	0.40	2.74

Table 2: Effect of different plant growth regulators on physical quality of fruits in sweet orange .

Tr. No.	Treatments	Fruit weight (g)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit Diameter (cm)	Number of segments per fruit	Fruit juice (%)	Number of seed per fruits	Weight of Pomace (g)	Weight of Rind (g)
T ₁	GA ₃ (100 ppm)	210.04	7.97	7.90	14.01	48.76	18.73	36.98	69.12
T ₂	NAA (100 ppm)	203.18	7.73	7.68	13.27	46.78	20.16	37.22	69.97
T ₃	CPPU (3 ppm)	215.76	8.20	8.06	14.21	49.69	18.92	35.66	68.17
T ₄	Salicylic acid (100 ppm)	196.12	6.96	6.92	11.02	41.12	24.58	38.01	71.05
T ₅	Triacantanol (500 ppm)	199.28	7.21	7.10	12.99	44.16	22.17	37.98	70.75
T ₆	Boron (0.2%)	200.32	7.09	7.01	12.26	43.12	23.18	38.00	70.99
T ₇	ZnSO ₄ (0.5%)	201.12	7.40	7.27	13.07	45.42	21.98	37.67	70.01
T ₈	KNO ₃ (0.1%)	204.22	7.86	7.46	13.57	47.08	19.36	37.02	69.58
T ₉	Control	179.11	6.89	6.81	10.02	38.71	25.82	38.81	72.23
S.E m. ±		3.68	0.11	0.11	0.63	0.52	0.38	0.54	0.68
C.D. at 5 %		11.08	0.33	0.32	1.91	1.55	1.14	1.62	2.04